

IMPACT PROPERTIES OF STITCHED FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

We studied impact properties of stitched glass/polypropylene woven composites at different temperatures. Remarkable improvements at low temperature (-20°C) of stitched composites were achieved. Besides, Stitching structures like stitch row orientation and stitch row spacing play an important role in changing the impact behaviour. Our results reveal that impact toughness can be improved by using high strength sewing thread and by increasing stitch density.

Keywords: Stitching; Fibre reinforced thermoplastics; Impact toughness; Fracture behaviour; Charpy impact

1. Introduction

Advanced fibre-reinforced composites have been widely used for structural components and engineering applications. Laminate composites usually exhibit low out-of-plane strength and damage tolerance, which will cause internal failures, such as delamination. To enhance the damage resistance and tolerance as well as damage characterisation of composites, several techniques are developed and reviewed [1,2]. These techniques have been the subject of much interest and extensive research, namely tough matrix materials [3], hybrid fibre composites [4,5], interleaving strips [6], modification of fibre/matrix interface [7-10] as well as 3D-weaving and braiding [11]. However, these approaches have some limitations such as high material and fabrication cost for developing a new matrix material and modifying the fibre/matrix interface and low in-plane strengths for 3D-woven and 3D-braided composites [12-14]. Recently, stitching the reinforcement in through-the-thickness direction is emerging as a new method because of its low costs, quick process and simple operation.

Many efforts have been made to investigate the mechanical properties of stitched fibre reinforced thermosetting polymer composite, particularly the impact properties. Improved damage tolerance and significantly reduced delamination area for stitched composites compared with unstitched ones are extensively reported [7,8,15-17]. Besides, stitching improves Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and reduces the influence of in-plane fibre orientation [18].

In contrast, a few studies proved that the stitching does not induce any significant improvement in damage resistance [19,20]. Jang studied Charpy impact behaviour of stitched composite made of Kevlar fabric and epoxy resin [21]. Although stitched

composites are superior in delamination resistance, the unstitched samples absorbed more energy than stitched ones. So far, sewing approach is mainly limited to the application of fibre reinforced thermosetting plastic composite such as carbon/epoxy and glass/polyester. Recently there is a growing interest in the use of thermoplastic resins as matrix materials instead of thermosetting matrix. Besides the advantages like low-cost manufacturing and possibility of recycle raw material, thermoplastic composites have advantages with respect to good damage tolerance and impact toughness [22]. However, it has not been reported up to now how the stitching influences the mechanical properties of fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, particularly under different temperature conditions. Except of Kevlar yarn, other kinds of sewing thread materials have also been rarely investigated.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the stitching effect on impact behaviour of a fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite made of glass filaments and polypropylene (PP) filaments. The effects of sewing thread material, stitch row orientation, and stitch density as well as temperature effect on the impact properties were detected. Impact properties were studied using an instrumented Charpy impact approach. A new PBO (Polyphenylenbenzobisoxazol) thread was chosen as sewing thread to find out whether this high strength thread will increase the impact toughness.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Twintex[®] - fabric (Saint-Gobain Vetrotex) made of E-Glass filaments and polypropylene filaments (PP) was used in this study. This twill weave fabric consists of the same number of warp yarns and weft yarns per unit area. Area weight of Twintex[®] - fabric is 745 g/m². Glass fibre volume fraction is 35 % and PP volume fraction 65%. Six plies with a size of 274 mm × 274 mm were stacked in the same orientation and then stitched using an industrial plain stitch sewing machine (Altin Textima). Applied sewing threads are given in Table 1. Lock stitch with 4 mm stitch length was chosen for tests. The stitched staples were then processed in a mould which was pressed at 200°C and under a pressure of 0.4 MPa for four minutes in a programmable press with built-in water cooling system. Specimens without stitches were also processed and tested in the same procedure as reference. The un-notched specimens were cut from laminates plates at a dimension of 3 mm × 8 mm × 85 mm. The detail dimensions, stitch rows, and stitch row orientations of specimens are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Specimen dimension and stitch row orientations: 90° and 0° stitch row directions, longitudinal and transverse with respect to the hammer edge

Table 1: Sewing threads listing and specifications of stitching for specimens for Charpy impact testing

Materials of sewing threads	Symbols
Unstitched	ON
Glass fibre, 132 tex, tensile force 62N, loop force 47N	GF 132
Glass fibre, 208 tex, tensile force 104N, loop force 82N	GF 208
Glass fibre, 282 tex, tensile force 130N, loop force 108N	GF 282
Glass and PP-filaments, 646.7 tex, Fibre volume fraction: GF 82.5 %, PP 17.5 %	GF/PP
Glass and PP-filaments, 132 tex, Fibre volume fraction: GF 24.4 %, PP 75.6 %	mGF/PP
Polyphenylenbenzobisoxasol, Zylon [®]	PBO
Twist of polyester yarn with thin carbon yarn	PES/CF
Polyetheretherketon, 72 tex	PEEK

2.2 Characterization

The Charpy impact tests were carried out using an instrumented impact pendulum (Zwick/Roell) in accordance with DIN EN ISO 179. The principle is shown in Fig.2a. A pendulum was equipped with load cells used for measuring the impact force. The impact energy was calculated by integrating the area under the load-displacement curve and by dividing this number by the cross sectional area of the specimen. Specifically, absorbed impact energy, W_B , and impact toughness, a_{cU} , are calculated according to

$$W_B = E_a - E_b \quad (1)$$

$$a_{cU} = \frac{W_B}{b \cdot h} \quad (2)$$

where E_a and E_b are potential energy before and after impact. W_B , b and h are absorbed impact energy, width and thickness of specimen, respectively. All specimens were tested at the same impact energy of 15 Joules. Three groups of specimens except PEEK, GF/PP and mGF/PP were tested at temperatures of -20 °C, 0 °C and 20 °C respectively. At least seven for each group were kept at temperature conditions for two hours.

Fig. 2b shows a typical force-deflection curve derived from an impact test on a stitched composite. The peak force (F_m) is the maximum force that the specimen can sustain on fracture, which indicates the beginning of significant damage. The associated energy absorbed up to this point is symbolized by E_m and it represents the energy to initiate

crack. After F_m , the dropping off in force indicates crack propagation. E_p represents the energy absorption in this phase. The total energy absorption E_t is

$$E_t = E_m + E_p \quad (3)$$

which is the entire area under the entire force-deflection curve.

Fig.2. (a) Schematic diagram of Charpy impact measurement and (b) schematic diagram of E_m and E_p of a force-deflection curve.

3. Results and Discussion

Overall, most stitched specimens have higher impact toughness than the unstitched ones (ON). The unstitched specimens show better impact properties at higher temperature than those at lower temperature. Apart from specimens with PBO and PES/CF sewing threads, most stitched specimens show much higher values of impact toughness at 0° stitch row direction, particularly at low temperatures. Only a marginal effect was found at 90° stitch row direction for different temperatures. The stitching effect on impact responses depends on either structures or properties of sewing threads as being discussed further in following parts.

3.1 Stitching effect on impact toughness

Typical force-deflection curves from an unstitched specimen and a stitched specimen with PBO thread tested at room temperature (20°C) are compared in Fig. 3. The traces of both unstitched (ON) and stitched specimen (PBO) show almost the same linear increase in force to the peak force (F_m) where some damage is initiated. After damage initiation, there is a sharp dropping off in force of the unstitched specimen. This implies that little energy was absorbed in the damage propagation process. However, the trace of stitched specimen shows a dropping off in several stages after the specimen reaches F_m . Hence, the gradual dropping off leads to a much higher deflection value associated with much more energy absorption. Therefore, in this case the total energy absorption of the stitched sample is more than twice higher than that of unstitched specimen. For stitched specimen under impact loading, the crack starts to grow between the plies until it is arrested by the nearest stitch. The stitching threads carry most of the load at the crack tip, the so-called ‘bridging effect’. As an evidence, the stitched specimen GF 282 reaches a higher maximal force (1.8 kN) compared to the unstitched one (1.5 kN) are

obtained from the force-deflection curve. Stitched specimens show obviously much shorter cracks after impact (Fig. 4). It is well known that a large crack resulting from delamination leads to a huge shortening of lifetime of structure service. Once the damage due to impact is reduced by stitching, the residual properties should be relatively improved [16]. Overall, stitching restricts the delamination size and propagation resulting in improved impact properties.

Fig.3. Deflection curves of an unstitched specimen (ON) and a stitched specimen (PBO) including PBO sewing thread at room temperature

Fig.4 Light microscope photos of fractured specimens at -20°C test temperature (a) unstitched, (b) stitched specimen (GF 282)

3.2 Effect of stitch row orientation

The typical force-deflection curves of specimens stitched with GF 282 sewing thread of both stitch row orientations (Fig. 1a) are presented in Fig. 5. It can be seen that the force of specimen having 0° stitch row orientation gradually decreases after F_m (Fig. 5a), whereas the force of the 90° oriented stitch rows shows almost a linear decrease (Fig. 5b). Therefore, the arrangement of stitch rows influences crack propagation behaviour. A splitting damage along the stitch line is observed from 90° stitch direction specimen (Fig. 5b). It is caused by local reduction of strength properties due to stress concentration at stitch holes. However, the impact toughness of the 90° stitch row direction is only marginally lower than that of the 0° stitch row direction, but it is still significantly higher than those of unstitched specimens. It indicates that the delamination is the dominate fracture mechanism during impact loading since the

stitching restricts delamination significantly on the specimen regardless of the strength degradation.

Fig. 5. Force-deflection curve of stitched specimen with sewing thread GF 282 in direction of (a) 0° and (b) 90°. Insert shows impact fractured specimen with sewing thread in 90° direction.

3.3 Effect of stitch density

Since stitching in a glass/PP composite contributes marginal differences to energy absorption of E_m , we applied here two approaches by increasing E_p to improve the impact toughness. One is using stronger sewing threads as described above. Another one is to decrease the slope of the force reduction after F_m so that a larger deflection and hence higher E_p can be achieved. This can be realized by reducing stitch row spacing, so that more stitches which are aligned transversely to the load direction can carry load.

Fig. 6. Force-deflection curves of stitched specimen with sewing thread GF 208 at 20°C, stitch row spacing of 3 mm and 1.5 mm. Insert shows comparison of impact toughness of stitched specimen with GF 208 in 3 mm and 1.5 mm stitch row spacing. Error bars represent standard deviations.

In order to compare the impact behaviour in propagation stage, stitch row spacing of 3 mm and 1.5 mm in 0° stitch row orientation were chosen. As shown in Fig. 6, the slope of force reduction of samples of 1.5 mm stitch row spacing is gradually compared to the samples containing 3 mm stitch spacing. The 1.5 mm stitch space results in double number of stitches in carrying the load, thus more energy will be dissipated and higher impact toughness is reached. The results reveal, by increasing stitch density will slow down the force reduction and hence increase the fracture toughness.

3.4 Dependency of impact toughness on temperature

In this section, influence of temperature is studied. The impact toughness values are compared at different temperatures for both unstitched and stitched specimens. As shown in Fig. 7a, the impact toughness of unstitched specimens decreases when the temperature drops down. It is because the polymer becomes more brittle. In sharp contrast, the impact toughness of stitched specimens tends to increase with decreased temperature. At -20 °C the impact toughness of stitched specimens including glass sewing thread (GF 282) is almost 2.5 times higher than that of the unstitched specimens. Such a considerable improvement is unexpectedly gained by stitching.

Fig.7. (a) Impact toughness of unstitched specimen (ON) and stitched specimen (GF 282) at different temperatures (20°C, 0°C and -20°C), 0° stitch row direction. (b) Comparison of energy absorption of E_m and E_p for unstitched specimen at different temperatures.

At low temperatures, less impact energy is supposed to be absorbed through polymer plastic deforming. The matrix material PP performs higher strength and stiffness which causes a light increase in value of E_m . A sharp decrease in deflection results in a significant reduction of E_p (Fig. 7b). Therefore, the total energy absorption E_t of unstitched specimens decreases considerably. At low temperature, delamination area is much larger since PP polymer is brittle and the crack tends to spread more quickly. For stitched composites however, the delamination growing will be strongly suppressed by stitching. In this way the stitching has probably much larger influence area. That is why

the impact toughness of stitched composite has positive correlation of decreasing temperature.

3.5 Correlation between energy absorption and sewing thread fracture work

The whole energy absorption (E_t) during impact fracture of stitched composites can be roughly attributed to fracture energy of base composite (E_c), bridging mechanism of sewing thread breakage energy absorption (E_s) and its pull-out fracture energy from base composite (E_{pl}), as described by

$$E_t = f(E_c, E_s, E_{pl}). \quad (4)$$

where E_c is constant for all sewing thread systems since they have the same base composite. E_{pl} depends on bonding behaviour of sewing thread in base composite and is unknown for different sewing thread systems in this study. $E_s = W_s \phi_s$ describes the breakage energy absorption of sewing thread by its volume fraction in base composite. W_s is the work done by tensile load on single sewing thread in Joule and ϕ_s is fibre volume fraction of sewing thread in percentage in base composite. The experimental data of E_t obtained from experiments against E_s are plotted in Fig. 8. Interestingly, almost all the data fall along a single straight line, showing that E_t increases linearly with E_s . It indicates that the impact toughness a stitched composite can be increased by using high strength sewing threads and by enhancing stitch density.

Fig.8. Dependence of E_t on E_s of different sewing threads. The insert presents a typically tensile force versus displacement curve of sewing thread, where the area under the curve is the fracture work (PES/CF: Polyester fibre; GF: glass fibre; GF/PP and mGF/PP: blend of glass and PP filaments)

Samples stitched with two sewing threads mGF/PP and GF/PP, which contain PP-filaments, show higher E_t values than the inclined line while the data from other sewing threads lie under this line. The higher values are indicative of possible higher E_{pl} which is contributed by pull-out energy of sewing thread. It is also easy to understand that PP inside sewing threads leads to a stronger bonding between sewing thread and base composite, especially for mGF/PP-sewing thread which contains 75.6% PP by volume fraction. The strong linear correlation reveals that by choosing high strength or high strain sewing thread (both of them contribute to fracture work) will enhance impact toughness of a composite. Increasing fibre volume fraction and controlling interface

bonding of sewing thread will further improve impact resistance of a stitched composite.

Eq. (4) can be written as

$$E_t = f(E_c, E_{pl}) + kE_s. \quad (5)$$

The slope k of this straight line in this study is 1.1. It indicates how strong the stitching influences impact toughness of a composite. This value depends on matrix type, fibre material and textile structure. For composites systems with other matrix materials, for example epoxy resin, the value of E_{pl} could be higher than PP matrix because epoxy could have a better bonding with strengthening fibres. This will likely lead a higher k value. To determine k for other composite materials, further study is needed.

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